

A LEXICAL-SEMANTIC ANALYSIS OF PAREMIES USED IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK PROSE WORKS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the important and advantages of paremies in prose works of English and Uzbek nation. Specifically, a reader can find the proverbs and sayings about marriage and love in English and Uzbek works and discover the equivalents and explanations in the given languages.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируются значение и преимущества паремий в прозе английского и узбекского народов. В частности, читатель может найти пословицы и поговорки о браке и любви в английских и узбекских произведениях, а также найти их эквиваленты и пояснения на данных языках.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek xalqlari nasriy asarlarida paremiyaning ahamiyati va afzalliklari tahlil qilinadi. Xususan, o'quvchi ingliz va o'zbek asarlarida nikoh va muhabbat haqidagi maqol va matallarni topishi, berilgan tillardagi o'xshashlik va izohlarini topishi mumkin.

Key words: proverbs, folk work, analyze, prose work, literature, national, linguocultural, phraseological meaning, comparative analysis, combination, expression.

Ключевые слова: пословицы, народное произведение, анализ, прозаическое произведение, литература, народное, лингвокультурное, фразеологическое значение, сопоставительный анализ, сочетание, выражение.

Tayanch so'zlar: maqol, xalq ijodi, tahlil, nasriy asar, adabiyot, milliy, lingvomadaniy, frazeologik ma'no, qiyosiy tahlil, birikma, ifoda.

Introduction: The trends of globalization and the interaction of cultures are combined by this modern era. Because of the ever-increasing scientific interest in linguistic phenomena, reflecting the cultural specifics of peoples and providing the relevance of choosing proverbial material as an object of research are the main purpose now.

Methods: It is commonly considered that Uzbek people are a nation as owner of a great heritage. The spiritual heritage left by our ancestors serves as an invaluable treasure for us. The proverbs describe the broad worldview, manners and ethics of our people, the expression of their thoughts. The educational value of the proverbs in our lives is incomparable.

Results: The peculiarity of our research consists in identifying of phraseological meaning, figurative means, lexical components, means of expressive syntax, as well as emotionally coloured lexical means and sound organization in the proverbs of the English and Uzbek languages of this thematic group. The object of the research was the English and Uzbek proverbs about marriage and love. The prose work of English: "Pride and Prejudice" by Jane Austen and Uzbek prose work: "Baxtsiz kuyov" by Abdulla Kodiriy served as the source of empirical material; the selection was carried out by the method of continuous sampling.

Discussion: The analysis of the proverbial field under study made it possible to know the importance of love and its meaning in human life:

There is no difference between a wise man and a fool when they fall in love.

Beauty is in the eye of the beholder.

Love is blind.

The heart that loves is always young.

The way to a man's heart is through his stomach.

Uzbek proverbs corresponding to them are:

Sevgida shoh ham gado ham bir. (Wise man and poor one are the same in love)

Hammaniki o'ziga – oy ko'rinar ko'ziga. (Averybody sees his/her lovely one as moon in the sky)

Sevgini ko'zi ko'r bo'ladi. (Love has blind eyes)

Sevgi yosh tanlamas. (Love doesn't choose age)

By using proverbs, the writer manages to express his opinion in a concise, understandable and effective way. Abdulla Kodiriy could explain a whole story through a proverb. He uses proverbs for bitter sarcasm or to make light laughs. Almost every writer tries to use proverbs effectively in his work. Here you can find such kind of proverbs and meaningful quotes about the topic used in Uzbek prose work "Baxtsiz kuyov":

Conclusion: Proverbs used in English literature, a critical attitude towards marriage and the mention of the advantages of a bachelor life can be found more often. In Uzbek proverbs in prose work, marriage is generally viewed more positively but almost half of the proverbs that reveal the hardships of life in marriage are proverbs that convey a woman's view of marriage.

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